

Proposing a New Framework for Optimizing Energy Consumption in Sensor Nodes Used in the Internet of Things

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Abstract: This paper presents a comparative analysis of evolutionary algorithms, including genetic algorithms, particle swarm optimization, cuckoo algorithm, and the Harris Hawk Optimization algorithm, for optimizing vehicle routing in smart cities. The study evaluates the performance of these algorithms in minimizing costs and maximizing efficiency in the context of providing services to requesters. Results indicate the effectiveness of the Harris Hawk Optimization algorithm compared to other approaches, suggesting its suitability for real-world applications in smart city environments. Future directions for research in this area are also discussed. **Keywords:** Evolutionary algorithms, Vehicle routing, Smart cities, Optimization, Comparative analysis. **1. Introduction** Smart transportation has emerged as an indispensable necessity and solution in today's traffic-congested cities. Urbanization presents significant challenges, including traffic congestion, pollution, and inefficiencies in transportation systems. In response to these challenges, smart cities have been developed, leveraging Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to promote sustainable development approaches[1]. A fundamental aspect of smart cities is the implementation of intelligent transportation systems, which optimize vehicle routing to minimize congestion, reduce travel time, and enhance overall efficiency. Evolutionary algorithms have gained prominence as effective tools for addressing complex optimization problems in smart transportation systems[2]. This research focuses on improving vehicle routing in smart cities using evolutionary algorithms, with a particular emphasis on the Hybrid Harris's Hawks Optimization (HHO) algorithm[3]. The HHO algorithm is a gradient-independent optimization technique inspired by the cooperative behavior and agile pursuit of Harris's Hawks in nature, known as the "surprise pounce."

Keywords: Internet of Things sensor networks, energy-aware routings, Sequirrel Optimization algorithm, Genetic algorithm

1. Introduction

IoT sensor networks are a special type of ad hoc networks that consist of a large number of sensor nodes. These sensors have limitations in power, battery, computing and storage. In an IoT sensor network, sensor nodes are widely distributed in a specific environment that periodically collect sensed data from the environment and then perform quantitative processing on it. Finally, they send the obtained information to the central station [1,29]

Despite the progress made in this type of networks, IoT sensor nodes with a large number and small size still rely on low-capacity batteries for their energy supply. Also, due to the type of structure of these networks, information transmission is facing security problems [2,30]. Besides, since the efficiency of IoT sensor networks depends on the coverage of its networks, the intensity of the network lifetime of the protocols provided in this type of networks, should be considered to increase the network lifetime. According to the definition, the time it takes for the energy of the first node to end from the start of the network is called the lifetime of the network. In order to increase the lifetime of the network, two criteria of reducing energy consumption and correct distribution of energy consumption between sensor nodes should be considered. Also, due to the use of this type of networks in harsh and inaccessible environments, it is not possible to recharge or replace the sensor nodes [3,38]. Therefore, one of the most important issues in IoT sensor networks is energy limitation severing. Also, since the efficiency of sensor networks is highly dependent on the network lifetime and its network coverage, it is vital to consider energy storage algorithms in the design of long-life sensor networks [4,31]. For this reason, it is important to use energy during the transmission of information packets and choose the right routing in the Internet of Things.

Cluster-based routing techniques are considered in IoT sensor networks, these techniques are compatible with sensor networks by having features such as energy efficiency, scalability, and lower latency, etc. [5,32]. In this method, the two steps of selecting the cluster head and routing through the cluster heads are important. By choosing these two steps correctly, it is possible to reduce the energy consumption of collecting data from nodes and sending them through the cluster head to the base stations, and then increase the lifespan of the WSN. Due to the dense deployment and unattended nature of IoT sensor networks, charging node batteries is very difficult. Therefore, a key issue for IoT sensor networks is to minimize energy consumption to increase network lifetime [6,33].

In the proposed method, by finding the optimal cluster head nodes based on the squirrel search algorithm and fuzzy prioritization of the cluster head nodes to form the optimal path, it obtained good results for the purposes of quality of service.

This paper is designed as follow. First the related researches in this field are described, then .

Related works:

Various methods and techniques have been considered to save energy consumption. Clustering method is one of these methods. In the clustering hierarchical structure, cluster heads consume

more energy due to processing, receiving, aggregating and sending data to the central unit. For this reason, the correct choice of cluster head can play a significant role in energy consumption and network lifetime. In [10,34], a cluster head selection algorithm based on the particle community algorithm is proposed, which aims to optimize energy in the network. Various parameters such as intra-cluster distances, distance to the sink node and residual energy in the sensor nodes have been considered in the development of the algorithm.

The particle community algorithm [11,35] is one of the meta-innovative algorithms that are inspired by the behavior of birds and creatures in the nature. This algorithm is used to find the optimal solution for a problem. The processing of this algorithm starts with a population of answers. Each member is called a particle. Every particle benefits from its own past and that of other members. In this algorithm, each answer is considered as an answer.

Each particle knows not only its best state (p best) but also the best group state (g best). Each particle adapts its speed and direction according to these two factors. In this method, each particle is considered as an answer. Each of these particles can be n-dimensional, which is determined according to the problem. At first, the speed and position of each particle is chosen randomly. Each particle has a value, by which it is evaluated, based on the objective function. The objective function is determined by the type of problem and its definition. The simple community algorithm easily stays in the local minimum and does not show the desired solution. The purpose of using g best and p best factors is to avoid early convergence and staying at the local minimum. How to calculate energy in the article is based on the model [12,37]. In this model, the transmitter's energy is spent on sending radio frequency and the receiver's energy is spent on receiving information. The amount of energy consumption in nodes depends on the volume of data and distance. The proposed algorithm includes two main phases of cluster head selection and cluster formation. The cluster head selection part is based on the particle assembly algorithm. In this phase, all sensors send their coordinates and remaining energy to the central unit to identify the nodes that have the ability to work in the network. In the second phase, cluster formation is done based on parameters such as distance, energy, and the ability to become a cluster head. In the proposed coding, CH contains cluster head indices, S contains sensor node indices, O contains sensor node coordinates that are randomly generated. In this article, only the energy parameter is considered, and there is no report of delay values in the network.

Another method is probabilistic clustering to aggregate data with the aim of optimizing energy consumption in IoT sensor networks. One of the most widely used clustering classes is the probabilistic class, which uses a probabilistic approach to select the cluster head. The main goal of the article is to optimize the number of clusters and how to distribute cluster heads in the network. The proposed solution of the article is based on the leach algorithm [13], which is one of the most widely used clustering protocols in IoT sensor networks. Leach tries to adjust the amount of energy consumption in the network by using cluster head rotation. In this method, the cluster heads are selected in a distributed and independent manner. To select each

cluster head, a random number r whose value is between zero and one is assigned to each node. But this method does not mention the delay parameters and calculation of processing and communication overhead.

Another method is clustering protocol based on fuzzy logic in heterogeneous IoT sensor networks. In [14], the researches have proposed a heterogeneous multi-level model for IoT sensor networks. Leveling is done according to a parameter called "model parameter". There are four levels 0, 1, 2 and 3 in the article model. The HEED model has been used to estimate the lifetime of the network. A HEED model is defined for each level (HEED-0, HEED-2, HEED-3, HEED-4). After evaluating the efficiency of this method, its phase structure is also introduced and checked. In this method, due to the use of the fuzzy method, the processing load has increased and it cannot cover all the dynamics and variability of the network.

In another solution that is based on the structure of data aggregation and transmission [15], a data aggregation and transmission solution is proposed according to the energy parameter, which one of its prominent features is frequent data aggregation in intermediate nodes. This point causes less energy to be spent on sending data. Also, the delay parameter has been investigated in the intermediate nodes, which has a significant impact on the routing efficiency. The article first mentions how to create topology, then how to select nodes and finally routing. In the proposed protocol, an objective function is used to select the leading neighbor node. A sensor node chooses a neighbor node to transmit and aggregate data. The selection of the neighbor node has a significant effect on the efficiency of data aggregation and routing. The selected neighbor node is the node with the highest cost function value. Then the data aggregation is done by the node near the source to reduce energy consumption, delay and traffic in the network. In structure-based data aggregation, data is collected in the form of a range of children and placed in a package. Also, the number of packets that are aggregated depends on the number of paths.

In data aggregation, it is done without depending on the structure in such a way that a timer is placed for each node, whose initial value is zero. In [16], the authors have reviewed the design challenges, how to collect and aggregate data in clustering and routing methods with the aim of energy optimization. They have suggested several important factors for the development of IoT sensor networks and their protocols, which are reported in a classified form in Table (1) [17].

Table 1: Important factors for the development of IoT sensor networks and protocols

Factor	Explanation
Network connection rate	Nodes share their information with each other and the central unit through IoT communication. When a node fails, it causes the network topology to change or part of the information to be destroyed.

coverage area	The area where the sensor nodes have the capability of mining and collecting data.
Node deployment	How to place the nodes in the network in such a way that the desired goals are met.
fault tolerance	The ability of sensor nodes when encountering errors and stopping transmission caused by factors such as lack of energy, environment and physical damage.
Routing	A process in which the route of sending data from an origin to a destination is determined.
Network changes	Change in network topology due to movement of sensors.

Table (2) shows the characteristics, advantages and disadvantages of structure-independent protocols.

Table 2: characteristics, advantages and disadvantages of structure-independent protocols

Structure	Protocol	Characteristics	Advantages	Disadvantages
Clustering-based	LEACH[13]	It randomly selects the cluster head nodes and tries to balance the energy by rotating the network	1) Each node has an equal chance to become a cluster head. 2) Using TDMA to avoid collisions	1) It has a high chance for a node with low energy to become the cluster head 2) Some nodes do not have a cluster head in the coverage domain
Chain-based	PEGASIS[24]	1) Nodes are organized as a linear chain. 2) A greedy approach is used.	1) Energy distribution is uniform 2) Reducing the energy overhead by using the dynamic network structure	1) It is necessary to have global information about the coordinates of the nodes 2) Reducing the number of sending nodes
Tree-based	EADAT[25]	The nodes with the most remaining energy and the shortest path to the sink node are selected	1) Nodes with more residual energy have a higher priority to become an intermediate node	1) The network density is considered in the central unit. 2) Load imbalance in the network

			2) The average residual energy of each node rarely decreases.	
Grid-based	GRID[26]	A set of aggregators is assigned to each grid.	Ability to adapt to changes and change the coordinates of nodes	Nodes located in the same grid cannot communicate with each other.

- A review of previous researches on energy-aware routing in wireless sensor networks using squirrel algorithm

In energy-aware routing in wireless sensor networks, data packet delivery from the source node to the destination node, which is called routing, is one of the basic issues. Many routing protocols have been designed for static or low dynamic networks. Some of them are designed based on the location of sensor nodes by using the squirrel algorithm, and some of them are designed without the need to locate nodes. Classification of algorithm routing protocols Squirrel is generally as follows:

1- Proactive protocols: In this type of protocol, which is also called Table-Driven, a table of routes is created before the routes are used. This table is used when sending data. The information that are kept in this table includes a list of destination nodes as well as steps with appropriate next steps to reach the destination. Proactive routing protocols in Squirrel algorithm do not have the long initial delays but incur a lot of overhead to build the table. On the other hand, the routes in the table may never be used. It is also possible that due to the long period of time between creating the table and sending data, some routes may become old and not suitable for sending data [8]. These types of protocols are not suitable for IoT networks.

2- Reactive protocols: In Reactive routing protocols, which are also called On-demand, the routes are not created before using, but when a node intends to send data to the receiver, the route discovery mechanism is performed, and then the desired route is created between the sender and the receiver. Data is sent [17]. These types of protocols suffer a lot of delay before sending data and are more suitable for dynamic environments, but they are not suitable for IoT networks.

3- Hybrid Squirrel Algorithm Protocol: Hybrid routing protocol in Squirrel Algorithm uses a combination of features of Reactive and Proactive protocols. These protocols create a lot of overhead to create the routes for the first time and every time because the node is mobile or it fails. The topology of the network changes [17].

A few similar researches have been done regarding energy-aware routing in IoT networks using meta-heuristic algorithms. In [21], a research has been done to design a multi-objective routing

in IoT networks using genetic algorithm. In this routing, the two criteria of energy and time delay are the constraints considered for routing. The proposed method provides a real-time routing. In [17], an energy-aware routing in IoT networks using particle swarm algorithm is proposed. In this research, by using a multi-stage particle swarm algorithm, constraints such as connectivity and all-diffusion are considered. In [22], another method using neural networks is presented. This research tries to increase the lifetime of the network by using clustering of sensor nodes. In [23 and 24], multi-objective routing in multimedia IoT networks with the ultimate goal of increasing network lifetime and using genetic algorithm is proposed. Also, in [25], a clustering-based routing method in IoT sensor networks using a hybrid algorithm of genetics and ant community is presented, in order to balance energy consumption in the entire network.

In all these researches, by using a meta-heuristic algorithm and by defining a suitable fitness function, it has been tried to realize the desired goals in routing such as increasing the network lifetime, reducing energy consumption, reducing time delay and other cases.

An overview of the genetic algorithm:

Nowadays, one of the prominent methods to solve a group of optimization problems is the use of methods known as optimization methods based on collective intelligence.

Evolutionary clustering algorithms, using evolutionary algorithms such as genetic algorithm, particle swarm optimization, ant colony optimization, etc., try to find the best possible solution for cluster construction. So that the resulting cluster has the minimum amount of energy consumption, the maximum amount of data sent to the well, etc. Algorithms [26 and 27] are examples of popular algorithms in the field of IoT sensor network clustering based on evolutionary algorithms.

Genetic algorithm [28] is a special type of evolutionary algorithm that uses biological methods such as inheritance and mutation. In the genetic algorithm, a chromosome is a set of indicators that defines a proposed solution for the problem that the genetic algorithm is trying to solve. The genetic algorithm starts by generating a random initial population. After the initial population is generated, a percentage of chromosomes are randomly selected as squirrels from the current population.

Squirrel chromosomes combine and exchange information between each other to create two child chromosomes. Also, in order to create more optimal children, the mutation method can also be used. After this step, the new generation is evaluated using the fitness function. A new generation is produced from the population of the best children and the population of the old generation.

Architecture:

One of the most important tools for obtaining information and understanding the environment, which has focused extensive research, is IoT sensor networks.

Routing protocols are one of the most important issues in IoT sensor networks, because these protocols are responsible for forming IoT communication paths. There are different types of construction algorithms, one of them is hierarchical routing protocols. In this protocol, the distance of nodes is not considered equal. The cluster head is responsible for collecting sensed data from common cluster nodes and sending them to the sink. The energy consumption can be evenly distributed among the nodes, and the data sent in the network can be reduced by data pooling. A key issue in IoT sensor networks is maximizing network lifetime. Network lifetime is especially important in IoT sensor networks where sensor nodes are usually remotely controlled.

One of the problems of this method is that the similarity and proximity of different nodes are not considered in sending data. In fact, in the method of this article, the network topology and how the nodes are placed in the data aggregation are not considered. Clustering can be used to solve this problem. In addition, the methods based on the network structure and the used topology, have a significant effect on reducing energy consumption. Some of these topologies are tree-based structures and clustering-based structures. Topologies based on clustering are among the most effective algorithms in optimal energy consumption. As a result, it can be said that the combination of clustering and data aggregation greatly increases the routing quality and reduces energy consumption.

In the proposed method, after clustering the nodes based on the Euclidean distance, in order to find the optimal cluster head node and having parameters such as the distance between the nodes and the remaining energy, the squirrel search algorithm is used inside each cluster, which is the task of sending data from the cluster nodes to the node. It is responsible for centralization and data collection, and on the other hand, the node selection algorithm, based on a new meta-innovative method. Also, after finding the optimal cluster head nodes in each cluster, in order to find the optimal global path between the origin node and the base station from fuzzy prioritization is used. Fuzzy membership function is used to specify the priority of cluster head nodes to be placed in the path between origin and base station as relay nodes. In the fuzzy membership function, two criteria of reliability and link quality (expected energy amount to send information packets to the next relay) will be used.

The aim of using the proposed method is to reduce the amount of data sent and received, and as a result, reduce the power consumption for communication. In general, by using this processing method, much less power is consumed in sending and receiving data.

Proposed method:

Suggested algorithm:

First, we state the assumptions of the network:

- 1) The size of the sensors is all the same and they have limited energy and are distributed in a square area.
- 2) The mobile stations are periodically monitoring the field and move randomly in a non-repetitive path.
- 3) Mobile stations have unlimited energy.
- 4) The location and ID of the sensor nodes are known and fixed.
- 5) Sensors can adjust their transmission power to the desired station distance.
- 6) In each period, after changing the location of the stations and temporary stop, it is executed, processed and published.

The proposed method includes two phases of identifying the coverage sensors of each station and determining the most appropriate mobile station.

The first phase is to identify the coverage sensors of each mobile station.

Wireless sensor networks consist of a number of sensor nodes that are spread across the sensor field and are responsible for collecting location information, which has different functions depending on the type of environment. These control sensors, which have a specific coverage range and limited energy, sense the data from the environment, and the mobile stations that periodically and randomly move between these sensors receive the data from them and send it to the control center. They transmit or broadcast the desired commands or messages among them.

After the network is established and the sensors are placed, the mobile stations that enter the environment must identify themselves to the network sensors. The way the mobile station works to identify itself in the network is as follows:

First uses a message to identify its location. The identification includes the number of the mobile station and the location information, they all broadcast between the sensors within a few paces, so that the sensors that are within a few paces of that station receive their message (Figure 3).

Figure 3: The first phase of sending an identification message through mobile stations

Then the sensors that receive the message, by examining the received messages, return a response message -that includes sensor number, location and cost- to the nearest sending station, and identify and introduce themselves as one of the sensors under control. then if each of this sensors receive a message from another station, it discards it.

In this way, the stations broadcast their location notification in the field and monitor the sensors that are adjacent or within a few steps of them. After sending the identification message and receiving the response message from the adjacent sensors, the mobile stations create an internal information table for themselves and according to the amount of data of each of their covering sensors, which indicates whether the sensory action is active or inactive. that is, it will record a value for it: it will take the value of zero for the inactive sensor and the value of one for the sensor that is active and sending data. Therefore, there will be a table for each of the mobile stations, which has a parameter of 0 or 1 for each sensor (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Creating a table with the identification of active and inactive sensors for each mobile station

As it can be seen, by creating such a table, a binary code will be considered for each of the stations, and with the calculation that is done with the objective function, the stations that have more active sensors in a certain period, as the most appropriate broadcasting station will be considered and the sensors that are not covering sensors of this station will be turned off at that stage and will help to save energy and increase their life span and the network.

This operation will be done in each period and in each period, the stations keep their path in each step so that they do not pass through it repeatedly in the next step. Other stations also do not cross at the desired places considering their crossing location. Otherwise, due to the operations repetition, the algorithm in question will not need to be optimized. And the energy consumed by the nodes to respond to sending messages from other stations will be reduced, which will lead to a reduction in the total lifetime of the network.

Phase two, determining the most appropriate mobile station in the routing algorithm:

Due to the dynamics of mobile stations and their number in the network, an optimal mechanism should be considered to manage the selection of mobile stations and information dissemination. The squirrel algorithm is one of the meta-innovative algorithms that are inspired by the way squirrels are hunted. In the wild, squirrels can find the coordinates of prey and then circle around it. Inspired by this behavior, this algorithm seeks to find the global optimal answer in the problem search space. Also, in this algorithm, each squirrel can be considered as an

independent agent that seeks to find the right answer for the problem in the environment. Using this pattern in nature provides a framework based on collective intelligence.

The chipmunk algorithm starts its processing with a random initial population of possible answers. Each of these answers is considered as a squirrel. Each squirrel contains two features, coordinates and coding. We assume that each squirrel contains a vector of size n (n is the number of clusters in the network). Figure 5 shows the structure of each chip in the proposed algorithm.

Figure 5: The structure of each squirrel in the algorithm

Each house of the vector (C_i) represents the number of the cluster and N_i represents the number of the mobile station. A mobile station is randomly assigned to each cluster. The random population should be such a number that all possible situations are examined. The required number of population is equal to the permutations without repetition of the number of mobile stations. After completing the initial population creation stage, each of the squirrels is evaluated. In the proposed routing algorithm, two objective functions that measure the amount of energy consumption and coverage have been used. It is worth mentioning that the node that is selected as a mobile station should have a higher energy level than the usual sensor network nodes. The objective function related to energy consumption is defined in relation (1):

$$E_{TX}(k, d) = E_{TX}(K) + E_{TX-map}(k, d) \quad (1)$$

In this regard, d is the distance to be sent and k is the number of bits sent or received. This relationship can be rewritten as follow:

$$E_{TX}(k, d) = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} k.E_{elec}(k, d) + k.\epsilon_{friss} d^2 & \text{if } d < d_{crossover} \\ k.E_{elec}(k, d) + k.\epsilon_{two-ray-ap} d^4 & \text{else} \end{array} \right\} \quad (2)$$

In this regard, the amount of energy consumption for receiving or sending when the distance in the threshold area ($d_{crossover}$) is of the second order d, but if the distance is greater than the threshold value, then the amount of energy consumption has a relationship of the fourth order with the distance. E_{elec} is the amount of energy used for receiving/transmitting, ϵ_{friss} is the amplification factor and $\epsilon_{two-ray-ap}$ is another amplification factor.

The second objective function is related to the evaluation of the network coverage by the mobile station. Equation (3) calculates how to calculate this objective function:

$$COV_j = \sum_{i \in n} ((p_{ji} + a + e_i) - m_i) * y_{ij} \quad (3)$$

In relation (3), y_{ij} is a binary value that is extracted from the mobile station table. If the i -th sensor is active in station j , the value of this variable will be one, otherwise it will be zero. E_i is the amount of energy consumed by the i -th sensor, p_{ji} is the cost of the path of the i -th sensor to the j -th satellite station, a is the energy required to turn on a sensor, and m_i is the remaining energy of the i -th sensor. In this objective function, the greater the number of active sensors in the desired station, the greater its fitness function will be and hence it will have a greater chance of being selected.

In the proposed algorithm, it is an optimal answer that can achieve a compromise of both objective functions. In multi-objective optimization problems, the final evaluation relationship should be defined in such a way that the effects of each function are considered. The relation (3-4) expresses the final goal function of the research:

$$f_j = C_1 * COV_j + C_2 * \frac{1}{E_{TX}} \quad (4)$$

In the above relationship, the lower the amount of energy consumed, the higher the value of the evaluation function (reverse relationship), but the function of the amount of coverage has a direct relationship with the final evaluation function. The higher the value of this function, the higher the value of the evaluation function. The values of C_1 and C_2 are the influence coefficients that are calculated experimentally. For example, if we want to give more importance to the amount of energy consumption, then $C_2 > C_1$. If we don't want to make a difference between the two objective functions, then $C_2 = C_1$.

The evaluation stage of the squirrels is done for t generations and for each answer. After this step is completed, the coordinates of the squirrels are updated. Equation (3-5) shows how to calculate the coordinates of squirrels:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{D} &= |\vec{C} \cdot \vec{X}_p(t) - \vec{X}(t)| \\ \vec{X}(t+1) &= \vec{X}_p(t) - \vec{A} \cdot \vec{D} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

In this relationship, t is the number of repetitions (generation), X_p is the coordinates and X is the coordinates of the squirrels. The values of A and C are coefficient vectors that are calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{A} &= 2\vec{a}\vec{r}_1 - \vec{a} \\ \vec{C} &= 2\vec{r}_2 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The value of a is in the range $[0 \text{ to } 2]$ and r_1 and r_2 are randomly assigned. The proposed algorithm has an iterative structure; the number of repetitions depends on the number of generations or the value of the convergence threshold. When similar answers are found for different generations, the algorithm is no longer able to find another optimal answer. For this reason, it is better to stop the algorithm and report the result.

simulation:

Using the Python programming language, the proposed algorithm for customizing the squirrel algorithm for routing in IoT networks was tested and investigated in order to properly distribute energy consumption in networks with different numbers of nodes.

The main implementation parameters are listed in the table 3.

Table 3: Algorithm Code Simulation's Main Parameters:

Parameter	Value
Size of each Squirrel	4
Number of Squirrels population	1000
Number of iterations	5000
Packet Length	4
Mutation rate in the nodes population	1%
Random Value generation function	Uniform
Matlab Version	2020

In the initial part of the program code, the main parameters are initialized. Then the coordinates of the network nodes are stored in two lists x and y . The population of squirrels is stored in a two-dimensional matrix. In each iteration of the algorithm, one percent of the population of answers (as weak answers) is removed and mutated answers replace them. Figure (6) shows the way of mutation in the proposed algorithm. In this figure, each antibody consists of four nodes, where node number one and four are the source and destination nodes, respectively. The other two nodes are intermediate nodes. In the bit replacement method, one of the nodes is randomly selected and its value is replaced with a random value. In Figure 6, the value 1 is replaced by 3.

Figure 6: Mutation in the proposed Routing Algorithm

The aim of presenting the proposed algorithm is to optimize energy consumption in IoT sensor networks. Optimum energy consumption also increases the lifespan of the network. The proposed research algorithm has been compared with the routing method based on the genetic algorithm [28].

In this simulation, we consider the number of independent routings, considering the origin randomly and sending an information packet that contains 4000 bits, and the lifetime of the network before the first node is destroyed. The result of these comparisons is shown in table (4).

Table 4: Comparison of Squirrel Algorithm implementation in the first and second cases

Network Lifetime	First Case	1386
	Second Case	1914
Mean of energy consumption after 1386 round routing (joule)	First Case	0.0952
	Second Case	0.1069
Standard Deviation of energy remaining of all sensor nodes after 1386 round routing	First Case	0.089
	Second Case	0.080

To compare the mentioned two modes, three measures of network lifetime, average energy consumption and standard deviation of the remaining energy of all sensor nodes, after the death of the first node that occurs in each of the modes, have been considered. The better the distribution of energy consumption between network nodes, the lower the standard deviation of the remaining energy of network nodes. As can be seen, in the second case, with the reduction of the standard deviation, the average energy consumption has increased, so in this case, by establishing a proper balance between the two criteria of energy consumption and the proper distribution of energy consumption, the lifetime of the network has been increased. In the second case, although the average energy consumption has increased, but considering the energy of nodes participating in routing, nodes with more energy have actually been used for routing. This issue increases the lifespan of the network. To compare the speed of convergence of two algorithms, squirrel and genetics, to find the optimal solution, we have considered the average execution time of 100 independent executions of these algorithms on the sample graph. All test conditions are the same for the two methods, such as graph specifications, fitness function, and other items. The only difference between the two methods is the type of meta-heuristic algorithm, which in one method is the squirrel algorithm and in the other method, the genetic algorithm.

By the time of finding the optimal path and the average number of generations for two algorithms, it is shown in table (5).

Table 5: Comparison of Convergence Speed of Squirrel Algorithm and Genetic Algorithm on the Sample Graph

Algorithm	Average of Convergence Time(second)	Average of Number of Generation producing
Squirrel	0.82	856.29
Genetic	1.43	1413.51

Squirrel algorithm finds the optimal solution faster than the genetic algorithm and with a lower average generation number.

Table (6) shows the execution result and Figure (7) shows the distribution of energy consumption after each round of routing for two algorithms.

Table 6: Comparison of Squirrel and Genetic Algorithms on a Sample Graph

Network Lifetime	Squirrel	1914
	Genetic	1752
Mean of energy consumption after 1752 round routing (joule)	Squirrel	0.115
	Genetic	0.109
Standard Deviation of energy remaining of all IoT Network nodes after 1752 round routing	Squirrel	0.097
	Genetic	0.099

Figure 7: How energy consumption is distributed after each round of routing

Table (6) and Figure (7) show the fact that the distribution of energy consumption in the squirrel algorithm is better than the genetic algorithm. By spending more energy, the squirrel algorithm tries to distribute energy properly, which ultimately leads to an increase in lifespan. However,

the squirrel algorithm tries to delay the death of the first node and increase its lifetime by sacrificing more energy. This causes the death of other nodes to happen more rapidly with the continuation of the network's life and assuming that the dead nodes are not replaced. Figure (8) shows the life cycle of the entire network

Figure 8: Life cycle of the entire network

The innovation used in the article can be summarized as follows, in order to reduce energy consumption along the route, taking into account a suitable energy consumption pattern, the shortest path between the source node and the destination node has been tried with the squirrel algorithm protocol, of course with the lowest The number of steps should be considered. Also, in order to control the proper distribution of energy consumption along the route, attention has been paid to the average remaining energy of the nodes; Therefore, in this protocol used in the squirrel algorithm, the lower the energy consumed in the path, and the higher the average remaining energy of nodes participating in routing, it means that the (low) consumed energy is distributed among more energetic nodes, as well The energy of IoT network nodes is reduced more optimally and the network energy runs out later; This leads to an increase in the lifetime of the network. It is clear that routing according to these two independent criteria is a multi-objective optimization problem and one of the hard non-polynomial problems, which can be solved using approximate methods.

Conclusion and future works:

Today, the technology of IoT sensor networks, with its wide spread, has been able to be useful and effective in the fields of crime, such as industry, smart homes, health, etc. Researchers and developers have conducted extensive researches with the aim of improving this technology as much as possible. This research has been carried out in the fields of security and access level, 5G technology, resource management and energy consumption. In this article, the problem of energy consumption optimization in IoT sensor networks is mentioned. In order to optimize energy consumption, a new routing algorithm based on squirrel optimization algorithm is proposed. Squirrel optimization algorithm is one of the innovative algorithms that are inspired

by the way squirrels are hunted in nature. This algorithm tries to find the optimal path in the IoT sensor network by using an initial random population of squirrels and evaluating them in different iteration times. The implementation of the proposed method was done with Python programming language and two parameters of energy consumption and lifespan were studied. To measure the efficiency of the proposed algorithm, a comparison between this algorithm and the routing algorithm based on the genetic algorithm has been made. Genetic Algorithms are one of the evolutionary techniques that were developed inspired by the theory of natural evolution. The simulation results show that the proposed routing algorithm can not only improve the energy consumption in the network but also increase the lifetime of the network. In future work, parameters such as security, delay, network load balancing, etc. can also be investigated.

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